

Questions, Comments and Answers following the presentation

Laser Frequency Combs in Astronomy, from La Silla and Armazones

Gaspare Lo Curto

Tristram:

1. *Can you explain what actually happens, when the fibre gets damaged at the end of its life-time?*
 2. *Is there any possibility of preventing such a damage, e.g. by cooling it?*
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1. *What we see are variations in the shape of the spectral envelope, and a progressive reduction of the spectral coverage. This seems consistent with the formation of color centers inside the fiber, where the energy density might become very large and which degrade the fiber faster and faster.*
 2. *Cooling has been considered, but it is expected not to affect significantly the behavior of the fiber with the current understanding of the damage mechanism. A lifetime test with cooling has not been performed on this kind of fibers to the best of my knowledge.*

Modigliani:

1. *Comment: LFC technology looks quite complex with ESPRESSO accuracy considering the already complex Paranal operation environment.*
 2. *As the fibre life time is short, is it a problem the fact you need to use different fibres during the ESPRESSO lifetime? Do you need to recalibrate each fibre to be consistent with previous measurements obtained with previous fibre within few cm/s accuracy?*
 3. *Is ESO the only observatory using this technology? if not, are you in contact with others to take into account of their experience to better operate ESPRESSO?*
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1. *The LFC will work mostly as a “black box”. From the point of view of the observatory it will be seen as yet another calibration lamp.*
 2. *Yes, we will have a “cross-calibration” procedure, although we expect no difference in the wavelength scale due to the PCF exchange. The lines position is not defined by the PCF, but by the atomic clock / GPS.*
 3. *ESO is not the only observatory experimenting this technology to calibrate its spectrographs. I am aware for example of similar tests carried over with HARPS-N at the TNG in the Canary Islands. Yes, we are in contact with other groups who are developing this technology.*

Smette: *The CTE in space telescope instruments degrade with time. We have not seen this effect on instruments on ground-based telescopes. However, do you plan to monitor this effect?*

Absolutely yes! This is included in the ESPRESSO calibration plan, and it could be done with LFC calibrations acquired at various signal intensity levels. An alternative could be the use

the Fabry-Perot source which gives a train of equally spaced lines, although their absolute position is not linked to an atomic transition like in the LFC.

Osip: In your plot for lifetime of photonic Crystal fibre, you show an effect at 600 h into operation. However, to my eyes, there appears to be an effect in the first 100 h. Does this imply a burn-in time?

We are investigating this. What you suggest is indeed a possibility.

Bristow: What kind of CTI correction are you implementing: empirical (function of signal, background, rows) or a readout model that attempts to return the flux to the original pixels?

CTI is function of the signal, and every parametrization must take this into account. We are trying to reconstruct the charge content of the individual pixels in the raw frames with a readout model parametrized using a specific calibration task: we will measure the variation of the PSF with the signal level, assume this is due to CTI and parametrize it using a model.